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Project: 1011361612 – SameMultiPhys –HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters in The Same Cell

DELIVERABLE D1.1

HANDBOOK OF MANAGEMENT

Due Date of Deliverable	M3	Completion Date of Deliverable	01/04/2024
Deliverable leading partner	UPM	Author	Blanca González
Signed off by		Person	Gustavo R. Plaza
WP no.	WP1	WP Title	Management
Dissemination level	Public		

Start date of the project	01/11/2024	Duration	48 months
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Coordinator:

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations may be used in this handbook:

CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statement
CV	Curriculum Vitae
DL	Deliverable Leader
DoA	Annex I -Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
PC	Project Coordinator
PLSIGN	Project Legal Signatory
PR	Periodic Report
PFR	Project Final Report
RTD	Research and Technical (or Technological) Development
SO	Scientific Objectives
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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1

Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the project management handbook

The objective of the SameMultiPhys Handbook on management is to offer a concise overview of all the necessary information needed for successful management of the project (including administrative protocols, financial matters, questionnaires after secondments, quality checks, etc.).

This handbook serves as a compendium of indispensable knowledge for proficient project management. It encompasses comprehensive details concerning management strategies, consortium structure, reporting protocols, requisite templates, publication procedures, and more. Additionally, it aims to elucidate any legal or financial nuances inherent in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement that may necessitate further clarification for beneficiaries.

It is important to note that this manual is dynamic and subject to modifications tailored to the evolving needs of the project. Updates will be implemented as necessary throughout the lifecycle of the SameMultiPhys project, augmenting the information provided and incorporating pertinent alterations in project dynamics or procedures. Each revision will be promptly communicated to all partners, detailing the adjustments made from the previous version.

1.2 Relation to other project documents (deliverables)

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Handbook on Management is overruled by Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

2

Project overview

2.1 Project summary

Biophysical biomarkers of cell state can provide insight into the underlying physiological changes that occur during disease progression. These biomarkers have the potential to revolutionize our understanding of cellular processes and provide an invaluable tool in the development of early diagnostics and clinical treatments. The use of single-cell techniques for imaging measuring multiple features of cells in real time has provided unprecedented insight into the complexity of cellular states. This project will explore the possibilities of developing single-cell technologies to measure multiple features on the same cell at once and evaluate their potential applications in biophysical biomarker discovery and diagnostics.

This project aims to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, ideas and resources between institutions with expertise in mechanobiology, engineering and materials science, to promote collaboration between researchers, and to develop innovative methods of basic mechanobiology research. The project will involve the use of advanced micro and nanofabrication techniques, advanced imaging techniques, and computational modelling to develop and validate the single-cell technologies developed. The outcome of this project will be the development of techniques to allow for the simultaneous measurement of multiple features on the same cell, which will open up new avenues in mechanobiology research and provide a valuable tool for the study of individual cells. The ultimate goal of this project is to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanobiology of cells, and to enable us to design and develop novel strategies for controlling and manipulating cell behaviour.

2.2 Project general data

Project number: 101131612

Acronym: SameMultiPhys

Call: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01

Topic: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01-01

Granting Authority: European Research Executive Agency

Grant managed through EU Funding & Tenders Portal: Yes (eGrants)

Project Name: Novel Biophysical Tools to Measure Multiple Parameters In the Same Cell

Consortium Agreement: Yes (not signed yet by all parties on 1st April 2024)

2.3 Participants

The list of Project Participants is included in the Grant Agreement, in the draft of the Consortium Agreement, and presented in the next list:

Table 1 – Participants of the project

No.	Role	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	Coo	Universidad Politecnica De Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	Ben	Tel Aviv University	TAU	Israel
3	Ben	Universita Degli Studi Di Firenze	UNIFI	Italy
4	Ben	Centre National De La Recherche Scientifique Cnrs	CNRS	France
5	AP	New York University	NYU	United States
6	AP	University Of Washington	UW	United States
7	AP	Universidad De Santiago De Chile	USACH	United States
8	AP	The Governing Council of the University of Toronto	UT	Canada

2.3 Duration, budget, and EC Contribution

The project started on **1 November 2023**, and is scheduled to conclude **48 months** later on **31 October 2027**.

The maximum grant amount of the project that shall be financed by the European Commission is **179,400.00 €**.

Detailed breakdowns of the budget allocated to each beneficiary and their corresponding EU contributions are provided in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement under the title "Estimated budget of the action."

The European Commission's contribution to each partner is contingent upon the acceptance of expenses by the EC, up to the partner's approved budget. This means that if a partner's expenditures fall short of its approved budget (or if the Commission does not approve all of its costs), the partner will receive only a proportionate portion.

2.4 Contractual documents

2.4.1 Grant Agreement (GA)

The Grant Agreement with the EC bears the reference project number 1011361612. This legally binding document, signed by all beneficiaries of the project, delineates the rights and responsibilities of the Consortium in relation to the European Commission. It comprises several annexes, including:

- Annex 1 Description of the action
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action
- Annex 2a Additional information on unit costs and contributions (if applicable)
- Annex 3 Accession forms (if applicable)2
- Annex 3a Declaration on joint and several liability of affiliated entities (if applicable)
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Specific rules (if applicable)

Access to the Grant Agreement and its annexes will be facilitated for all project partners through the "partner's repository" link, which is exclusively accessible to project partners.

Grant Agreement Amendments

A modification to a Grant Agreement (GA) constitutes a legally binding adjustment altering the commitments outlined in the original agreement. Such adjustments can introduce new entitlements or obligations for the involved parties, providing the Consortium with the flexibility to adapt the GA over its duration.

Amendments must be documented in writing and channelled through the project coordinator. The process involves the exchange of letters:

- ➔ A letter-request initiated by the coordinator acting on behalf of the consortium.
- ➔ A letter of acceptance of the amendment, also issued by the coordinator representing the consortium.

It's important to note that any proposed project amendment necessitates official approval from the EC. Significant alterations to Annex I (Description of the Action) or administrative details pertaining to project partners, budget, etc., require formal acceptance by the EC through the amendment process.

The project coordination team strongly advises partners to consult with the project coordinator regarding any matters that may warrant an amendment.

2.4.2 Consortium Agreement (CA)

The Consortium Agreement serves as the internal contract among the consortium partners, signed and agreed upon by all involved parties. It establishes the internal regulations governing project management, delineates the organizational structure of the Consortium, and outlines decision-making processes. However, in the event of any inconsistencies, the terms of the Consortium Agreement are overruled by those of the Grant Agreement.

The project Consortium Agreement will also be accessible to all partners via the "partner's repository" link, which is exclusively accessible to project participants and partners.

3

Project structure

3.1 Work packages list/overview

SameMultiPhys is a 48 month project organized in the following Work Packages:

Table 2 – Work Package (WP) List

WP No.	WP title	Activity type	Number of person-months	Lead beneficiary	Start month	End month
1	Management	Management	0	UPM	1	48
2	Designing and fabricating new prototypes	Research	5	CNRS	1	34
3	Standardizing measurements with calibration samples	Research	3	UNIFI	13	24
4	Testing and validating prototypes	Research	16	CNRS	13	47
5	Quantifying images and performing statistical analysis	Research	3	TAU	3	48
6	Refine: evaluation of the prototypes for improvements	Research	7	UPM	25	47
7	Developing biophysical models of cell response	Research	5	UPM	25	48
8	Dissemination and communication	Dissemination, Communication	0	UPM	1	48

The Work Packages structure and a WP relation, as defined in the Description of Work, is the following:

Figure 1. Workplan

The detailed description of each Work Package's work is described in Annex I to the ECGA, Description of Action (DoA). Each Work Package has a named WP Leader that is the partner in charge of the leadership and coordination of the technical and economic aspects of the Work Package. This includes responsibility for the preparation of any technical reports, achieving milestones, achieving deliverables and provision of deliverables to the Coordinator on schedule, provision of interim and progress reports to the Coordinator on schedule. The partners concerned shall appoint a named individual to carry out the role of Work Package Leader.

3.2 Deliverables

Each Work Package (WP) within the SameMultiPhys project is associated with specific deliverables. It is important that thorough tracking of all deliverables is maintained throughout the project's duration.

The list of deliverables spanning the 48-month timeframe of the project is provided below. The list is organized chronologically to facilitate monitoring of deliverable submissions. If a deliverable consists of multiple versions to be submitted on different dates, each instance of the deliverable is listed alongside its respective release month (#). Partners responsible for these deliverables must exercise caution in ensuring timely submission.

Table 3 – Deliverables list

WP No	Deliverable No ¹	Due Date (month) ²	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Type ³	Dissemination Level ⁴
WP1	D1.1	3	Handbook on management	UPM	R	PU
WP8	D8.1	6	Dissemination and Communication Plan and Communication "toolkit"	UPM	R	PU
WP8	D8.2	6	Data Management Plan	UPM	DMP	PU
WP8	D8.3	6	Exploitation Plan	UPM	R	SEN
WP1	D1.2	13	Progress report	UPM	R	SEN
WP1	D1.3	18	Mid-term meeting	UPM	R	SEN
WP3	D3.1	20	Report of the calibration samples to perform standardizing measurements	UNIFI	R	SEN
WP3	D3.2	24	Protocol for the fabrication and biofunctionalization of calibration samples	UNIFI	R	SEN
WP4	D4.1	24	Report of the results of calibration methodology verification	CNRS	R	PU
WP4	D4.2	24	Report of the results of verification using cell lines	CNRS	R	PU
WP2	D2.1	32	Design of microfluidic system to perform multiparameter, biophysical and same-cell assays	CNRS	DEM	SEN
WP2	D2.2	34	Technical parameters of the fabrication process of microfluidic devices	CNRS	R	SEN
WP2	D2.3	34	100 units of microfluidic system to perform multiparameter for prototype testing	CNRS	DEM	SEN
WP5	D5.1	36	Report of analysis of image data, including technical data analysis	TAU	R	PU
WP5	D5.2	36	Scripts to perform automatic analysis of acquired data	TAU	OTHER	PU
WP6	D6.1	48	Report of quality analysis and results of verification in the refined prototype	UPM	R	PU

WP7	D7.1	48	Report of numerical analysis model	UPM	R	PU
WP7	D7.2	48	Outline of the biophysical biomarkers identified, and related potential meaningful relationships in the data	UPM	R	PU

¹Deliverable numbers in order of delivery dates. Please use the numbering convention <WP number>.<number of deliverable within that WP>. For example, deliverable 4.2 would be the second deliverable from work package 4.

² Measured in months from the project start date (month 1).

³Please indicate the nature of the deliverable using one of the following codes: R = Report, P = Prototype, DEM = Demonstrator, DMP= Data Management Plan; OTHER = Other.

⁴Please indicate the dissemination level using one of the following codes: PU = Public, SEN = Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

Submission of Deliverables

During the course of the Project, the deliverables identified in Annex I to the Grant Agreement have to be finished and submitted to the EC according to the timetable specified in the Deliverable list. All deliverables have to be submitted electronically via the EU Funders & Tenders Portal.

In case any kind of delay is detected, this should be reported to the Project Coordinator, so the necessary corrective actions are taken, and the EC officer is kept informed.

3.3 Milestones

The list of milestones spanning the 48-month timeframe of the project is provided below.

Table 4 – Milestones list

Milestone No	Due Date (month)	Milestone Name	WP No	Lead Beneficiary	Type
1	3	Consortium Agreement	WP1	1 - UPM	Public report
2	6	Kick-off meeting	WP1	1 - UPM	Meeting minutes and presentation

4

Project management

4.1 Management structure

The project management structure is the following:

Figure 2. SameMultiPhys management structure

4.1.1 Project coordinator

The coordinator, Prof. Gustavo Plaza, representing UPM, is dedicated to the management of the project. In this capacity, he will bear the following responsibilities:

Communication:

- Facilitating all correspondence between the project and the Commission.
- Organizing and overseeing general assembly and project meetings, including administrative tasks and minutes.
- Compiling and disseminating annual project progress reports to the Executive Board.

Global Monitoring of Work Progress:

- Monitoring and adjusting the project's schedule as necessary.
- Overseeing overall progress across all work packages and implementing procedures for detailed progress.
- Supervising budget expenditures and allocations and providing support regarding project administrative matters.
- Coordinating payments to project partners.
- Managing reporting activities, including deliverables, progress reports, and annual management reports, and ensuring that paper documentation is submitted to the European Commission.

In addition to the project coordinator, as shown in Figure 2, other entities have been established within the project framework. These include the coordination team and the Executive Board, comprised of the Work Package (WP) leaders from each beneficiary institution, as well as the leaders of associated partners, who represent the associated partners involved in the project. A concise overview of them is provided in the subsequent subsections.

The PC shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the GA or this CA. The PC shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in CAN and in the GA.

4.1.2 Coordination team for management support

Figure 3. Coordination Team

The PC together with members of the UPM institution, will oversee work progress through the following means:

→ **Quality assurance:** The quality assurance body will be led by an Assistant Professor (Blanca González, UPM), to support the PC in monitoring progress and providing quality assurance effectively. Functions include:

- ✓ Perform the pursuit of progress work involved with technical-administrative aspects.
- ✓ Assistance and coaching at administrative level to the partners.
- ✓ Quality Management. Providing a quality assurance model to collect information, people in charge of its delivery, terms of delivery, revision of the deliverables of the project, etc (see Figure 4).
- ✓ Preparation of the project meetings in collaboration with the coordinator.

Figure 4. Quality assurance of the WPs

→ **Project Management Support:** Project managers (Beatriz Cubeiro and Ivette Trinidad, UPM), with large experience in European Project Management will assist the day-to-day management of the Project. They will be responsible for:

- Managing Financial Operations: This role involves providing comprehensive support to the consortium regarding financial matters throughout the project, including: a) Monitoring the eligibility of costs, b) Reviewing partners' financial statements, c) Assisting the coordinator during audits, d) Facilitating the distribution of payments to partners, and other related tasks.

- Managing Consortium Coordination: This encompasses various responsibilities such as: a) Developing templates for essential project documentation, b) Verifying the reporting documentation produced by the coordinator and partners, c) Ensuring proper execution of tasks, d) Maintaining regular communication with partners to address queries or issues, e) Supporting the preparation of Technical Review Meetings, among other duties.

→ **Scientific Support:** A team of several professors of the Department of Materials Science from UPM (Gustavo V Guinea, José Pérez, Rafael Daza, Francisco J Rojo, and Blanca González) will work to support the PC in all the scientific activities that need to be discussed within the project. Project managers functions include all contract amendments to be presented to the European Commission. The partner UPM will be responsible for implementation of changes and contributes all of the necessary documentation.

4.1.3 Executive board: work packages leaders

The Executive Board will be an executive committee responsible of the decision-making for the project. Member of the board will consist of the coordinator and one senior representative from each beneficiary organization who has the authority from his or her contributing organisation to take any necessary corrective action. The senior representatives will be, unless an unforeseen circumstance, Dr. Pierre Joseph (CNRS), Prof. Costanza Montis (UNIFI) and Prof. Yael Roichman (TAU). The Chairman of the board will be the PC, Prof. Gustavo Plaza (UPM).

Meetings of the Executive Board will be held M1 (kick off), M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42 and M48 (final meeting). During these virtual meetings the results obtained will be discussed and it will be prepared and approved the consecutive reports. Planning in detail the tasks to be implemented before the next meeting. The final meeting is to monitor the fulfilment of the programme and the quality of the results, based in the general objectives of the proposal (as in the deliverables and expected results).

The Executive Board will have a strong focus on monitoring the exploitation plan according to the rules laid out in the consortium agreement. This committee will review all scientific results to ensure that any valuable Intellectual Property is identified and protected at an early stage and disclosed in an organised manner.

The Executive Board will ensure the timely execution of tasks included in each Work Package, stimulating the interaction between the various partners involved. They are also responsible for the consolidation of the specification reports and execution of the tasks that integrate each WP. Each organization involved will appoint a WP Manager, who is responsible for operational decisions, sending quarterly a short progress report to the Project Coordinator supported by the management team, guaranteeing that the partial and total objectives of the WP are accomplished, elaborating the reports of the WP, and organizing the presentation of results.

4.1.4 Associated-partner leaders

The associated partners leaders, Prof. Craig Simmons (UT), Prof. Claudio García-Herrera (USACH), Prof. Liam J Holt (NYU) and Prof. Juan C Del Alamo (UW), will:

- Manage the respective secondments in their institutions, related to the Person-months of each WP.
- Be responsible for the necessary resources within the work package and liaise with contributing partner institutions.
- Discuss the approach and methodologies taken with the Executive Board as appropriate.

4.2 Management procedures

4.2.1 General management procedures

Beneficiaries are responsible for:

- Effective economic management and conduct of the operational work in accordance with the program guidelines and with ethical and legal standards.
- Complying with general terms and conditions governing grants and any terms and conditions specific to each grant or granting programme established by the European Commission.
- Managing and supervising operational personnel and seconded staff.
- Meeting reporting requirements specific to HE and the call
- Acknowledging, whenever possible, Coordinator's financial support for the operational work.

4.2.2 Decision taking mechanism

Decisions must consistently be made at the appropriate decision-making level. To ensure this, the roles and responsibilities of each Consortium body are clearly outlined in the project Consortium Agreement.

For a Consortium Body to deliberate and make valid decisions, a quorum of two-thirds (2/3) of its members must be present or represented.

Each member attending or represented in the meeting shall hold one vote.

Decisions will be reached by a majority vote of two-thirds (2/3) of the total votes.

4.2.3 Monitoring and progress reporting

Every WP leader shall provide updates on project advancement to the Project Coordinator every six months in the meetings. These updates will encompass technical advancements, outcomes, deliverables, adherence to the WP schedule, as well as the monitoring and mitigation of identified risks. The PC will receive support from management throughout this process, including the review of legal and administrative matters.

4.2.4 Risk management

Effective risk management strategies allow a project manager to identify the project's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. So, to ensure SameMultiPhys's success, it is important to define how to handle potential risks, mitigate or avoid problems.

In the GA the foreseen risks are gathered joint to their description and mitigation measures. The risk-management procedure to be implemented will be as follows:

- Any partner or member of the project (including associated partners) is able to identify another potential risk within the project beyond the foreseen ones and shall immediately inform the Coordinator.
- Coordinator will assess the dimension of the issue and its impact on the milestones and deliverables of the project. Coordinator will be also responsible, together with the partners involved and, if needed, with the work-package coordinators, will define potential mitigation measures and he will submit them to obtain the beneficiaries.
- Coordinator may also initiate the breach procedure before the informing the beneficiaries if one partner is responsible for a severe failure in fulfilling its responsibilities within the project.

4.3 Meetings

During the project, a Mid-term meeting (Deliverable) will be held in between month 14-18 in EU/AC. In this meeting, REA Staff (external experts), beneficiaries, associated partners and seconded staff will be gathered.

The objective of the meeting is to discuss the status of the project, the financial arrangements and mitigating measures and to meet seconded staff.

The Coordinator's role in the Mid-term meeting will include the following responsibilities:

- At least 6 months in advance agree on time and location
- Establish meeting Agenda with PO and inform Consortium
- Ensure participation of Seconded Staff
- Ensure submission of Mobility Declarations

5

Project reporting

5.1 Continuous reporting to the European Commission

5.1.1 Deliverables

As described in DoA, the complete list of deliverables to be submitted to the Commission is available in section 3.2 (See Table 3: List of deliverables). Besides, from this list, there are specific deliverables aimed at monitoring and reporting the progress of the work and implementation of the project:

- Data Management Plan due Month 6
- Plan for the dissemination and exploitation of results, including communication activities due Month 6
- Progress Report due Month 13
- Mid Term Meeting due Month 14 18

As recommended by the EC, no Personal data should appear in "Public" deliverables.

5.1.2 Mobility declarations

Mobility declaration for secondments must be submitted within 20 days from start of secondment through the Funders and Tenders Portal: Documentation for this procedure can be found in the following website:

→ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=60850187>

Exchanges between EU/AC in the same sector ("interdisciplinary") are subjected to the following conditions:

- Only applicable to the project if validated at GAP.
- Maximum eligible: 1/3 of months funded by EU implemented.
- If more than 1/3: deduction of costs at the end of the project.

It is also Mandatory to provide the seconded staff the **SE Information Package**. The PC will send the following reference to all seconded staff to download the information package:

→ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/20778>. European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, Information note for Marie Skłodowska-Curie staff members in Staff Exchanges, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023,

5.1.3 Submission of questionnaires after secondments

Based on Article 18. of the grant agreement, funded MSCA fellows are requested to submit two questionnaires about their experience: one immediately following the completion of the fellowship ("Evaluation Questionnaire") and one two years later ("Follow-up Questionnaire"). Please note that, as a MSCA Staff Exchange participant, you should complete each form only once, immediately after and two years after your last secondment.

We strongly value the opinions of all participants funded through the programme and your responses to these questionnaires will help us shape the future design of the MSCA.

The **Evaluation Questionnaire** can be accessed through the following link:

→ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MSCAEndOfFellowshipHE>

and the **Follow-up Questionnaire** can be accessed through the following link:

→ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/MSCAFollowUp2years>

Seconded staff will need to enter project related information, including the project number and acronym.

5.2 Periodic reporting

Monitoring the project implementation is a continuous task that takes place at any moment during the active period and beyond. There are contractual tasks that make the project monitoring most relevant at certain periods in project's life, in particular after each reporting period at the time of payments. In accordance with the Grant Agreement, project reporting obligations with the Commission are the following:

- First Periodic Reporting module opens at M24.
- Final Periodic Reporting module opens at M48:

The submission of the periodic reports to the European Commission is the responsibility of the PC, who will use the electronic exchange system.

At the end of each reporting period, the Commission shall evaluate and approve project reports and deliverables and distribute the corresponding payments.

5.2.1 Technical periodic reporting

Each Periodic Reporting module includes 1 Technical report with the following content:

- Part A: completed in the Funders and Tenders portal, where Information in Continuous Reporting automatically transferred.
- Part B: uploaded word document

The technical periodic reporting procedure will take 4 months will consist of:

1. 2 months before the Reporting Period deadline and 4 months before its submission, the Project Coordinator (PC) will send to every WorkPackage Leader (WPL) the technical periodic template with instructions.
2. 1 month later (1 month before the end of the reporting period), the WPL will send the PC the first Technical Periodic Report Draft.
3. The PC will have 3 weeks to check it and send comments to the WPL.
4. WPL will have 3 weeks to prepare the second draft and send it to the PC.
5. Then, the PC will have 15 days to send that 2nd draft with additional comments to WPL.
6. 15 days before the submission, WPL will send comments to the PC in order to finish the Final Version of the Technical Periodic Report.
7. PC will be in charge of submitting the Part B in the Participant Portal.

5.2.2 Financial periodic reporting

Each Periodic Reporting module includes 1 Financial Statement. The Financial Report consists of structured forms from the grant management system, including:

- Individual Financial Statements (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary (and third parties).
- Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties, from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned.
- Periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

All beneficiaries - including the coordinator - must fill in their own financial statement, electronically sign it and submit it to the coordinator. Coordinator submits full Periodic Report to REA. The procedure will take approximately 3 months:

1. 15 days before the Reporting Period deadline, the PC will remind all partners to complete their Financial Statements and send them a template where he will try to gather all the information related to the Use of Resources in order to be updated about the financial progress of the project.
2. Each beneficiary will have up to 30 days to fill and upload their financial statements in the Participant Portal.
3. 5 days after Financial Statements having been uploaded, the PC will check them.
4. 15 days before the submission deadline, the PC will ask the Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) for locking their financial statements.
5. Each Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) from each beneficiary will have approximately 12 days to check, sign and submit the Financial Statements.
6. Once all Financial Statements and Technical Periodic Reports have been uploaded, Project Coordinator will be able to submit.

Further guidelines for reporting are available in the Funders and Tenders' online manual:

→ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=1867970>

5.2.3 Mobility declarations

Important considerations regarding mobility declarations are the following:

- They must be encoded before submission of Financial Statement.
- They cannot be in "Draft" when Periodic Report is submitted.

6

Templates

Templates for the following documents will be facilitated for all project partners through the "partner's repository" link, which is exclusively accessible to project partners:

- 1) Meeting agenda template
- 2) Meeting minutes template
- 3) Deliverable template
- 4) Technical report template
- 5) Financial report template

The project logo must also be included in all the documents related to the project.

The templates could suffer modifications during the project duration, so it is recommended to download the templates from the partner's repository each time an official SameMultiPhys's document is going to be generated.

7

Recommendations

7.1 Keeping records

Partners must for a period of five years after the payment of the balance — keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible. The beneficiaries must keep the original documents. Digital and digitalised documents are considered originals if they are authorised by the applicable national law.

For this reason, it is recommended opening a folder with the name of the project and subfolders to have all the information required organized:

→ Financial information

- Personnel costs related to secondments
 - Time sheets signed (writing and approved by the persons working on the action and their supervisors)
 - Contracts
 - CVs
- Subcontracts
 - Invoices and payments
 - Offers
 - Contracts
- Materials
 - Invoices and payments
- Equipment
 - Invoices and amortization and payments
- Secondments
 - Flights
 - Accommodation expenses
- EC Payments and beneficiary payments
- Financial Statements submitted to EC

→ Technical information

- Periodic reports and final report

If an audit might carry out, which could be started up to two years, after the payment of the balance, all this information should be prepared, and one person related to the project (PC may be suitable) should help the auditor to solve his/her doubts.

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References

Main documents which have been used as references in order to develop this handbook have been the following:

- SameMultiPhys Grant Agreement
- Description of Action
- [Horizon Europe Programme Guide for Applicants](#)
- Templates